

Deep Caries Management

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Abstract

Worldwide, the prevalence of dental caries is still significant. When dental caries is not treated, it can extend into the dentin, causing inflammation, infection, and eventual pulp damage. However, conservative treatment approaches can promote pulpal healing, even in cases of extensive decay. Caries can be managed by diet modification which leads to change in the biofilm preventing the nutrient supply of the tooth. This way caries can be controlled by partial excavation without much damage to tooth structure. Effective management of deep caries relies on evidence-based treatment strategies and proper education on managing pulp exposure. Maintaining a healthy pulp is essential for the long-term stability of the tooth, as it supports natural defense mechanisms. Contemporary conservative dentistry prioritizes pulp preservation using minimally invasive approaches.

Definitions

Deep Caries

Caries reaching the inner quarter of the dentin, yet separated from the pulp by a layer of firm or hard dentin, can be identified on radiographs, especially on interproximal or occlusal surfaces. Recognizing this distinction is crucial for determining appropriate treatment strategies that prioritize pulp preservation while controlling disease progression.. During the surgical treatment, pulp exposure is a possibility.¹

Deeply Seated Caries

Dentine-thickening caries is radiographically visible when they are present on an occlusal or interproximal surface. The exposure of the pulp during surgery cannot be avoided.¹

Affected Dentin

Firm & leathery in texture. Strength are determined by the balance of mineral content and collagen, which play a crucial role in its structural composition.. Can be scraped off with more pressure. Does not contain microorganisms. Can be mineralized

Infected Dentin

It is soft in consistency due to a lack of minerals & collagen. Can be scraped off with gentle pressure. Contains microorganisms. They cannot be remineralized. It should be completely removed in cavity preparation.

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Introduction

Dental caries is the microbiological destruction the hard structure of the tooth weakens over time due to mineral loss, resulting in demineralization and increased susceptibility to damage. localized portion tooth due to various factors like dietary carbohydrates, dental plaque, and cariogenic bacteria. Because Concerns about the invasive nature of traditional dental treatments, along with the risks of overtreatment and the repetitive cycle of restorations, have led to the adoption of minimally invasive, biologically based treatment

approaches². As a result, the management of deep caries has transitioned from complete removal of decayed tissue to selective removal, reducing the likelihood of pulp exposure³. Extensive carious lesions are classified into two radiographic categories: deep and extremely deep. This classification helps assess the risk of pulp exposure and may also

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indicate the point at which pulp inflammation becomes more severe and potentially irreversible⁴. Effective caries management focuses on eliminating microbial irritation and preventing further bacterial infiltration by using advanced dental biomaterials that shield exposed dentin and pulp from external factors..

Aetiology

The dental biofilm consists of both commensal as well as non-invasive microorganisms. According to the ecological plaque hypothesis, frequent carbohydrate consumption disrupts the microbial balance, allowing acidogenic and aciduric species to thrive, leading to caries⁵. Streptococci, Lactobacilli, and Bifidobacteria initiate the demineralization of the tooth surface. As carious lesions progress, the microbial composition becomes more diverse, with increased levels of *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacillus* species. Additionally, other bacterial taxa, including novel *Prevotella* species, *Selenomonas* species, *Eubacterium* species, and *Fusobacterium* species, have also been identified in advanced lesions⁶.

Response of Tooth To Caries

The dental-pulp complex responds to irritation through a process that involves both inflammation and mineralization, maintaining a delicate balance between tissue damage and repair to preserve pulp vitality⁷. When caries develop, bacterial acids, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), and metabolic byproducts from plaque penetrate toward the pulp, moving against the natural flow of pulpal fluids. This triggers an increase in odontoblast activity, leading to the formation of tertiary dentin as a protective response⁸. The outermost layer of exposed dentin undergoes degradation due to acid activity and bacterial enzymes, causing demineralization within the zone of sclerosis².

Diagnosis

A thorough patient history, detailed examination of the affected tooth, and additional diagnostic tests, such as radiographic assessment for clinical decision-making to be effective, caries depth and clinical indicators such as symptoms, progression rate, and color sensitivity tests are crucial⁹. Radiographs should clearly display the entire tooth, including at least 3 mm of apical tissue beyond the root tip, without any interproximal overlap, distortion, or processing errors. The depth of a carious lesion can be estimated using bitewing radiographs, while CBCT provides a more precise diagnosis of lesions¹⁰.

How To Detect Carious Dentin

Dentin hardness is regarded by many general dentists as the most crucial factor in caries excavation because it contains minerals or collagen. Infected dentin is soft and its texture is comparable to cottage cheese due to the presence of collagen network & minerals. Affected dentin is firmer than infected dentin. It could be described as having a leather-like consistency. Clinically, soft, discolored, and moist tissue can be used to identify the first active carious environment.

How to Manage Deep Caries Without Pulp Exposure

The removal of carious tissue can be carried out either in a single-step procedure¹¹ or through a stepwise two-stage approach¹², depending on the clinical condition of the tooth. These methods are typically considered when the tooth shows no

symptoms or presents with indications of reversible pulpitis.. Round burs and hand excavators are commonly used in less intrusive removal of carious tissue techniques¹¹. Methods for removing carious tissue in one or two stages appear to be an effective approach to reducing the risk of pulp exposure.¹³ Regardless of the selected carious tissue removal technique, it is essential to remove decay from the cavity's periphery until only hard dentine remains, ensuring optimal bonding and effective sealing from the oral environment. On the pulpal aspect, preserving soft or firm dentine may be beneficial in reducing the risk of pulp exposure. Further more, before the placement of a definitive resin-based composite restoration, a conventional glass-ionomer cement may be applied as a protective barrier over the dentine¹⁴.

Reparative Dentin Bridge Formation

The goal is to form a barrier of hard tissue protection. After the primary odontoblasts are lost as a result of direct pulp exposure, Defects in the pulp-dentin are corrected. by the formation of a hard tissue barrier formed by pulp-derived cells¹⁵ of which are induced by using appropriate biomaterial.

Balance Between Inflammation And Repair in the Dentine-pulp Tissue Complex

The DP complex depends on a delicate equilibrium between repair and inflammation to sustain its health. When irritants are eliminated and an appropriate restoration is placed, the pulp has the ability to recover and maintain function. However, if inflammation dominates, leading to ongoing caries progression, the protective dentine structure weakens, allowing deeper bacterial infiltration. As decay advances into the tertiary dentine layer, the pulp undergoes increasing levels of inflammation, which may escalate to localized infection and tissue breakdown, ultimately leading to pulpal necrosis if left untreated.⁴⁵

What to be Done When the Caries is Approaching the Pulp or There has been Pulp Exposure

Treatment options include procedures like indirect & direct pulp capping.

Procedure for pulp capping: Preventing external irritation of exposed tissue is the main goal of pulp capping. mostly caused by bacteria.

History of Pulp Capping

In the 1990s, dental adhesive materials used in direct pulp caps initially produced positive results¹⁶; however, after a few months, the marginal bond deteriorated and was then invaded by bacteria, causing pulpal inflammation or necrosis. Resin-based adhesives were not widely recommended¹⁷, prompting the development of biologically driven materials aimed at supporting the formation of mineralized bridges¹⁸

Indirect pulp capping: The procedure of placing material on a delicate layer of carious dentin in immature permanent teeth that, if removed, may result in pulp exposure. is known as “indirect pulp capping.”¹⁹ Although this method has been debatable for years, it now exhibits remarkable success in non-symptomatic teeth without radiographic signs of pathosis.²⁰ Indirect pulp capping is indicated When decay is near the pulp, or the remaining dentin thickness is below 0.5 mm. On the pulpal floor, when covered by only firm or soft dentin, caries excavation should be

done to place a biomaterial that acts as a dental barrier, followed by which a permanent restoration can be placed.¹

Two-stage: Soft carious dentine is excavated in the first stage such that there is enough space for proper placement of a temporary restoration. This method of selective caries removal requires two visits. Altering the cariogenic environment is the goal of the first stage, to the extent necessary for an effective temporary restoration to be placed., selected removal of decayed dentin. is carried out to carious dentine. The initial soft dentine turns into more hard & dark dentine with time. The second stage of caries removal is performed after a few months, allowing the remaining dentin to change in texture, making it easier to remove. During this period, a protective base, such as calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) or hydraulic calcium silicate cement, is applied to promote healing. The tooth is then restored using a glass-ionomer material to ensure proper sealing and protection..

Determining when the excavation should be terminated during the clinical procedure (one or two stages) is a significant challenge. The presence of voids beneath the restorative material during the remineralization process is an essential factor to evaluate. These voids may increase the risk of lesion reactivation, affect the stability of the restoration, and lead to additional complications.

Direct pulp capping: Direct pulp capping involves sealing an exposed pulp site with a biomaterial to promote the formation of reparative dentin and preserve pulp vitality¹⁹. This procedure is recommended in cases of pulp exposure caused by trauma, caries removal, or tooth preparation. Direct pulp capping, however, may not be the best option for pulp tissue that has experienced acute inflammation and has been exposed to oral microorganisms for a prolonged period of time.

Steps in Pulp Capping

1. In order to achieve favourable results for direct pulp capping, the careful removal of caries under dental dam isolation, with the aid of optical magnification and a caries detection dye, is crucial for effective treatment.²¹
2. Tissue haemostatic; The most widely accepted method to control haemorrhage of exposed pulps is by placing gentle pressure on the exposed area with cotton pellets dampened in saline or sterile water helps manage bleeding and safeguard the pulp. Laser and electrosurgical haemorrhage control have shown limited effectiveness²². However, NaOCl has been promoted since the late 1950s as a successful hemostatic agent for direct pulp capping and is an accepted antimicrobial irrigant used in orthograde endodontic therapy.²³ Several advantages of NaOCl solutions demonstrate its superiority over other agents. This agent aids in the chemical amputation of fibrin and blood clots, the removal of biofilm, the clearing of dentinal chips, cavity interface disinfection, The removal of compromised cells at the exposure site and effective hemorrhage control are crucial for successful pulp management²⁴. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solutions, with concentrations between 5.25% and 8.0%, primarily target surface pulp cells while preserving deeper tissue²⁵. To ensure proper bleeding control, NaOCl is applied for approximately 5 to 10 minutes.

3. Carefully place a thin layer of biomaterial over the exposed site using a small ball applicator or similar instrument. Use a dry cotton pellet to remove any excess moisture. Apply a minimal amount of flowable compomer, light-cured resin, or a glass-ionomer liner to cover the biomaterial. Apply 34% to 37% phosphoric acid gel to the remaining cavity walls for 15 seconds to enhance adhesion, then rinse thoroughly. Gently dry the cavity, ensuring the dentin stays slightly moist. Apply the bonding agent and cure it following the manufacturer's instructions. Complete the restoration with composite material and ensure proper curing. Regularly assess pulp responsiveness every six months and conduct radiographic evaluations every three to six months or as needed²¹.

The Final Restoration

If microleakage is reduced or eliminated, the pulp has the best chance of healing and surviving²⁶. To Ensure a reliable seal against microleakage for optimal long-term restoration success. the appropriate restorative material for each case must be carefully selected and the delivery executed with a high level of skill²¹. Conservative restorative treatment that best preserves Maintaining the intact tooth structure significantly improves the potential for pulp survival.¹²⁷

Materials used for Pulp Capping

For effective pulp capping, the material should have the following essential properties³¹:

- Encourage the development of reparative dentin
- Preserve the vitality of the pulp
- Release fluoride to reduce the risk of secondary caries
- Possess antibacterial properties to inhibit bacterial growth
- Form a secure bond with dentin
- Be compatible with restorative materials
- Withstand mechanical forces during placement and throughout the restoration's lifespan
- Maintain sterility to prevent contamination
- Be radiopaque for clear visibility in radiographic imaging
- Provide a strong barrier against bacterial penetration
- **Ca(OH)₂** : Recognized as the standard material for pulp capping²⁸, it promotes the natural formation of mineralized tissue. This process often leads to the development of porous osteodentin. However, when applied directly to the pulp, the resulting mineral barrier is irregular, does not bond effectively with the dentin walls, and fails to establish a complete seal.²⁹, Tunnel defects in the dentin,²⁹, lack of adequate sealing, time dependant dissolution and lack of antibacterial properties. Clinical trial that have been conducted over a period of time reveals that the success rates of calcium hydroxide which is commonly used as a pulp capping agent in carious exposures were unsuccessful, not reliable for the long term and uncertain.³⁰ After two years beneath the pulp capping material Ca(OH)₂ was found to have flaws in the reparative dentin formation.

- **Mineral Trioxide Aggregate:** MTA has been shown to stimulate the formation of mineralized tissue beneath exposed pulp and aids in the healing process. to preserve pulp vitality. MTA's biocompatibility and sealing ability are due to the material's dominant calcium ion, It interacts with phosphates in tissue fluid, leading to the formation of hydroxyapatite.³¹ The layer thus formed is a critical feature that helps to form a seal between MTA and the dentinal walls. Production of calcium silicate hydrate and calcium hydroxide is done by mixing water with Tricalcium & dicalcium silicate. The most significant disadvantage of MTA is its long duration of setting. (5 hrs)³² difficulty in handling the material, heavy metals in its composition leading to the discoloration of the material. Furthermore, Pulp capping procedures are made easier by using MTA as it shows less toxicity leading to reduced pulpal inflammation than Ca(OH)²³. An analysis of clinical studies spanning 9-10 years suggested that MTA-treated pulp-capped teeth demonstrated favorable long-term results achieved 92.5-97.96% success.³⁴ According to recent research, MTA's performance was superior regarding the bond strength compared to that of composite or rinse adhesive.³⁵
- **Calcium Silicate-Based Cements (CSCs):** These advanced cements primarily consist of dicalcium and tricalcium silicate, components also present in MTA and Portland cement. Their hydraulic properties enable rapid strength development upon hydration. Research has demonstrated that these materials promote angiogenesis and regulate transcription factors²¹. Additionally, calcium silicate cements (CSCs) exhibit bio inductive capabilities that facilitate cell proliferation, differentiation, and the formation of hard tissue barriers, which are essential for pulp healing. Their minimal inflammatory response makes them highly suitable for pulp capping. Furthermore, with a setting time of approximately 10 minutes, CSCs provide an efficient solution for single-visit pulp capping and pulpotomy procedures³⁶.
- **Biodentine :** It has a fast set time of ten minutes and impressive properties that actively interact with biological tissues, supporting healing and tissue regeneration interact with biological tissues to promote healing and regeneration. useful for both indirect and direct pulp capping procedures. The cement has no effect on human fibroblast cytodifferentiation and has no genotoxic/According to the Ames mutagenicity test³⁷, the compound has been evaluated for potential cytotoxic effects. As a pulp capping agent, it is biocompatible with pulp tissue, aiding in the recruitment of odontoblast-like fibroblastic cells and supporting the development of a calcified barrier comparable to MTA.³⁸
- **Theracal LC :** It is Calcium silicate-based which can be light cured and used as DPC and IPC material, allowing immediate final restoration placement.³⁹ Calcium and hydroxide ions are released by TheraCal LC. The bioavailability of calcium ions released by TheraCal LC has been demonstrated to be in levels lower to biodentine in terms of stimulatory activity.⁴⁰ The presence of a resin matrix alters its setting mechanism resulting in decreased ability to

produce calcium.⁴¹ It showed greater performance when compared to Biodentine or MTA because of its sealing ability & reduced microleakage.⁴² When layered with composite or glass ionomer cement, TheraCal LC has higher bond strength values than Biodentine⁴³

Future Directions in Deep Caries Management

Advancing approaches to preserve pulp vitality is essential for minimizing invasive procedures, reducing the need for repeated restorative interventions, and improving long-term tooth retention. To ensure a uniform, evidence-based approach, it is necessary to integrate current research into both undergraduate and postgraduate dental education. Significant differences in treatment standards for managing deep caries and pulp exposure highlight the need for greater consistency in clinical guidelines.

A collaborative effort among Cariology and Endodontic specialists is vital to develop standardized, research-backed protocols that can be applied across primary and secondary dental care settings. Establishing well-defined clinical recommendations will help reduce variations in practice, ensuring that all patients receive effective and consistent treatment based on the latest scientific evidence.⁴⁴

Conclusion

A paradigm shift in conservative dentistry has occurred due to the development and use of newer dental materials like MTA, Biodentin, and Growth factor with pulp capping material. The standard of dental care is shifting in favor of more conservative and regenerative treatment options like vital pulp therapy. The principles of pulp capping are to control bacteria, halt caries progression, Inducing pulp cells to produce new dentin with a sound seal that protects the pulp. Selective caries removal strategies can be one-visit as indirect pulp treatment or two-visit using a stepwise approach. Understanding the biology of caries, being aware of technological advancements, and believing in better restorative materials have led to the beginning of a pulp preservation program that is both beneficial to the dentist and the patient.

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